

CORPUS BASED TRANSLATION STUDIES

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Annotation: This article delves into a particular parallel development within the fields of linguistics and translation studies: the analysis of language use through the lens of corpus-based research. In recent years, there has been a surge in the compilation of translation corpora, specifically designed to explore the linguistic features and characteristics of translation. These corpora are often used to compare translated texts with their non-translated counterparts.

The interactions between corpus linguistics and corpus-driven translation studies are explored through an examination of perceptions of translated texts and the underlying assumptions underlying corpus-based approaches. Corpus-driven translation research is situated within the broader theoretical landscape of translation studies, and attention is drawn to the significance of contextualizing translation by integrating corpus-based inquiries with other methodologies and analytical approaches.

From the perspective of a scholar of translation interested in corpus-based research, it is immediately apparent that the scope of linguistic domains addressed in general introductions to corpus linguistics, such as those by Biber, Conrad, and Reppen (1998), McEnery, and Wilson (2001) and Kennedy (1998), does not encompass translation.

Tony McEnery and Andrew Wilson, for instance, delve into a plethora of linguistic subjects, including lexical analysis, grammar, semantics, pragmatics, discourse analysis, sociolinguistics, stylistics, text linguistics, historical linguistics, dialectology, variation studies, and psycholinguistics. Additionally, they explore related fields such as language and linguistics teaching, cultural studies, and social psychology. However, the teaching of translation is mentioned in a single paragraph within the section on language teaching. The dearth of focus on translation studies may stem from the relative novelty of corpus-based approaches in this field, or possibly from a tendency towards a uni-directional exchange of knowledge between linguistic and translation research.

The corpus-based approach undoubtedly holds significant potential within the broader theoretical framework of descriptive translation studies. It appears to offer a method for describing language use in the context of translation.

Unlike many multilingual corpus linguistic studies, corpus-based translation research focuses on translation not in terms of its relationship with the source text, but rather as an independent instance of text generation and communication. The discussion on what constitutes translation is crucial for several reasons.

Firstly, researchers' perspectives on the concept of translation serve as a critical foundation for applying corpus-based methodologies to the study of translation. These perspectives determine the choice of the object of study — what type of translation, when it was produced, by whom and for what purpose — serving as the basis for decisions regarding corpus design and representativeness. The selection of specific texts for inclusion in a corpus, which will later be used for the study of a particular type of translation, is a critical step in this process. This decision is also crucial for the analysis and interpretation of the data, as it provides clarity on the concept of "translation" that these data are describing.

Corpus analysis not only focuses on observable phenomena but also on regular, typical, and frequent occurrences. This approach directly relates to the norms discussed by scholars in the field of descriptive translation studies.

Much of the previous corpus-based research in translation studies has concentrated on syntactic and lexical features of translated and untranslated texts, which may provide evidence of processes such as explicitation, simplification, and normalization. It is important to note that while translators may sometimes consciously attempt to produce more explicit, simplified, or normalized translations, the use of corpora can also be seen as a means of investigating aspects of translator language use that are not the result of deliberate and controlled processes. Although translators may not be aware of these processes, the translated product can provide indirect evidence of the cognitive processes inherent in translation.

A common view of corpus-based translation studies is that they provide a methodology that allows linguistic and cultural approaches to translation to be integrated, and the impact of ideology on translation can be studied (Tymoczko, 1998; Kohn, 1996). These aims relate to tracing the link between text and context, as well as between "regularities of actual behavior" (Toury, 1995) and "interests and stakeholders." Hermans is less optimistic about the potential of corpus-based studies in this regard, arguing that "text-crunching" can reveal something about the linguistic features of texts, but not about their significance, i.e., whether translations are peripheral or central at a given point in a specific culture (Hermans, 1999).. Although acknowledging the potential benefits of

corpus-based research in translation, Mason (2001) cautions against disregarding the rhetorical aims that govern language use. A focus on concordance data may lead to a neglect of contextual and collocational factors. He emphasizes the significance of considering the influence of genre, discourse, and textual intention on the choices made by the source author and translator, as well as other considerations such as the communicative goals of both the text producers and the translator's orientation or purpose.

This task cannot be accomplished through vague generalizations based solely on quantitative data. Instead, it requires a comprehensive approach that combines quantitative and qualitative analysis to delve into the intricate nuances of discourse, genre, and textual design. This is undoubtedly the most challenging aspect of corpus-based analysis, whether applied to translated or non-translated texts.

There is ample room for improvement in the methodological approaches used in this field of research. While quantitative "text-crunching" may appear relatively straightforward, it is essential to recognize that corpora offer specific types of data, such as frequency lists and concordances, which must be integrated into a coherent theoretical framework. These data must be combined with information from other sources to move beyond the superficial or obvious.

Moreover, the absence of direct speech and contracted forms in corpora differs significantly from their representation in a comparable literary corpus from the British National Corpus.. It is evident that a corpus-driven analysis of translations and comparable texts cannot independently verify the above statement (a). To accomplish this, analogous studies on moderation in other languages, both in translated and non-translated texts, must be conducted, as well as further investigations of other English texts and their translations.

Regarding (b), a lower frequency of moderators in translations may be correlated with other evidence suggesting that translators clarify ambiguity and render explicitness on multiple levels. To further explore this aspect of the translation process, it would be beneficial to investigate other gradable adverbs in a similar manner and compare them with non-gradable intensifiers (e.g., completely, absolutely, totally, utterly), which, due to their lack of ambiguity, are less likely to undergo processes of disambiguation or explication in translation.

The present paper stems from the conviction that corpus-linguistic approaches are indeed instrumental in exploring various facets of translation. In fact, technological advancements have made these methods increasingly

valuable for the general study of language (McEnery & Wilson, 2001, p. 195; Kennedy, 1998, p. 294).

Nevertheless, this concise discussion underscores the intricate nature of some of the fundamental issues in translation studies, which extend far beyond the realm of linguistic data analysis and lexical, syntactical, and semantic investigations. Corpus-driven translation studies must first address the concept of "translation" itself, the universality of translation as a practice, and the characteristics and norms of translation before proceeding to compile corpora and gather data. The analysis of data on translation products cannot be dissociated from the study of the process of translation. The «features of translation», which are discussed in this work and throughout much of the literature on corpus-based translation research, could perhaps be more accurately described as «features of the translation process», as they refer to cognitive processes such as simplification and explicitation that may be constrained or influenced by social, cultural, and other factors.

However, our methods for empirically examining these aspects of the translation process fall short of perfection. The necessity to contextualize translation and its study requires us to approach it holistically, which limits the usefulness of predominantly quantitative analyses based on corpus data. To truly «go beyond the words on the page», as Mason (2002) suggests, we need to engage in qualitative analysis and explore data beyond those extracted from corpora. Thus, while translation research benefits from the incorporation of corpus-linguistic techniques for the former, the latter necessitates a fusion of corpus-driven investigations with analyses of literary, societal, historical, ideational, and cognitive contexts.

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